

Removal of chromium(VI) from aqueous solutions using mango leaf powder : Process optimization with Response Surface Methodology

Soma Nag^a, Abhijit Mondal^a, Umesh Mishra^b and Sudip Kumar Das^c

^aDepartment of Chemical Engineering, National Institute of Technology Agartala, Agartala-799 046, Tripura, India

^bDepartment of Civil Engineering, National Institute of Technology Agartala, Agartala-799 046, Tripura, India

^cDepartment of Chemical Engineering, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : somanag.nita@gmail.com, abhijitju17@gmail.com, umishra123@rediffmail.com, drsudipkdas@vsnl.net

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Abstract : In the present work, a naturally available mango leaf, was investigated for removal of Cr^{VI} from aqueous solution. In a series of batch experiments, kinetics and equilibrium of sorption process were studied with respect to pH, initial Cr^{VI} concentration, adsorbent concentration, time, particle size and temperature. External mass transfer model and intra-particle diffusion models were used to predict the rate limiting step. Both had contribution in adsorption process but the internal diffusion was the rate controlling step. Numerical values of the coefficients indicated that the adsorption was quite fast. The kinetics was best described by pseudo second order model. Langmuir monolayer adsorption model was the best fitted one among the four isotherm models used. Sorption energy estimation by using Dubinin-Radushkevich model predicted the process was chemisorptions. The high temperature was found favourable, and the thermodynamic study suggested that the adsorption process was endothermic and spontaneous. A two-level two-factor full-factorial central composite design with the help of DESIGN EXPERT 7.0 statistical software, was used to optimize the process conditions for the maximum removal of Cr^{VI} from aqueous solution.

Keywords : Mango leaf, external diffusion, intra-particle diffusion, mass transfer coefficient, Dubinin-Radushkevich model, Response Surface Methodology.

1. Introduction

Cr^{VI} contamination in aqueous system is a serious health hazard. The increase in industrial activities over past few decades have resulted the significant presence of Cr^{VI} in aquatic environment. It is toxic, non-biodegradable and can cause several diseases in human bodies, like, diarrhea, stomach and intestinal bleedings, cramps, liver and kidney damage^{1,2}. Therefore, waste water should be treated at source before reaching the water bodies. Adsorption process has received great attention of researchers for heavy metals removal due to its high effectiveness, economic feasibility and environment friendliness^{3,4}. The lingo-cellulosic materials had attracted the interest of researchers for biosorption of heavy metals onto it. The lingo-cellulosic materials contain a large number oxygen-containing functional groups and these groups

take part in metal binding activity and are the key factor in promoting the irreversible adsorption⁵.

The aim of the present study was to value addition of the waste mango leaves for use as a bio adsorbent and to understand the governing mass transfer mechanism for Cr^{VI} adsorption process. The optimization of the process variables was conducted by using Response Surface Methodology (RSM). The kinetic and equilibrium models were studied and model parameters were evaluated. Sorption energies were predicted by using Dubinin-Radushkevich model. Thermodynamics of adsorption process were studied to find out the changes of Gibbs free energy, enthalpy and entropy. A two-level two-factor full-factorial central composite design with the help of DESIGN EXPERT 7.0 statistical software was used for optimization.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Preparation of adsorbents :

Mango leaves were gathered from NIT Agartala, Tripura, India campus and sun dried for 15 days after washed with double distilled water. Then, the dry leaves were grinded in a Philips grinder and further dried in an oven at 60 °C for 6 h. The powder was sieved to obtain desired particle sizes of -22+44, -44+52 and -52+60 mesh, equivalent to average particle diameters of 575, 325 and 270 μm respectively, and stored in air-tight containers.

2.2. Preparation of standard Cr^{VI} solution :

1000 mg L⁻¹ of Cr^{VI} aqueous stock solution was prepared using A.R. grade K₂Cr₂O₇. The standards for calibration and test solutions of range 20 to 100 mg L⁻¹ was prepared from the stock solutions.

2.3. Analysis of chromium(VI) ions :

The analysis of chromium(VI) ions in the standard and treated solutions was determined spectrophotometrically by using a UV-Spectrophotometer (Lambda-25 UV-Vis, Perkin-Elmer, USA). A purple colour was developed with 1,5-diphenylcarbazide as the complexing agent⁶. The absorbance of the purple coloured solution was read at 540 nm after 10 min.

2.4. Reagents and processes :

All analytical grade chemicals, K₂Cr₂O₇, H₂SO₄, NaOH and 1,5-diphenylcarbazide from E. Merck India Limited, Mumbai, India, were used for experiments. The pH of the solution was measured with a EUTECH make pH meter which was previously calibrated with standard buffer solutions. The density was measured by specific gravity bottle and the surface area was measured by BET apparatus, Chemisorb 2720, Micrometrics Instruments Corporation, USA. Surface was characterized by using Scanning Electron Microscope, JSM 6390, JEOL, Japan. FTIR analysis was carried out in Nicolet IS 5 FT-IR Spectrometer of Thermo Scientific Ltd., USA to find out the functional groups responsible for adsorption.

The batch experiments were conducted in a Remi make magnetically stirred 2L beaker with known strength of Cr^{VI} solutions. The studies were conducted at three different temperatures at a stirring speed of 180–200 rpm for all experiments.

All the investigations were repeated in triplicate and the average values were reported. It was observed that the reproducibility and the relative deviation were in the order of ±0.5% and ±2.5% respectively.

2.5. Experimental design and optimization by Response Surface Methodology (RSM) :

A two-level two-factor full factorial centre composite rotatable design (CCRD) was employed in this optimization study and for that DESIGN EXPERT 7.0 (Stat-Ease Inc., Minneapolis, MN, USA) software was used. The central composite design (CCD) is the most frequently used under Response Surface Methodology (RSM) design. The RSM consists of a group of empirical techniques devoted to the evaluation of relationship existing between a cluster of controlled experimental factors and measured responses according to one or more selected criteria. In this experiment initial concentration and adsorbent dosage are the independent variables selected to be optimized for the adsorption process. Percentage of removal (%) and adsorption capacity were taken as the response of the design experiments. The coded and uncoded (actual) levels of the independent variables are given in Table 1. Thirteen experiments are required to be performed with two replications are carried out at the center points to evaluate the pure error.

Once the experiments are performed, the response variable (removal % and adsorption capacity, mg/g) was fitted a second-order model in order to correlate the response variable to the independent variable. The general form of the second-order polynomial equation is as follows :

$$Y = \delta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_i \chi_i + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_{ii} \chi_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=i+1}^k \delta_{ij} \chi_i \chi_j + \alpha \quad (1)$$

where Y is the response (dependent variables), δ_0 , the constant coefficient, δ_i , δ_{ii} and δ_{ij} the coefficient for the linear, quadratic and interaction effect, χ_i and χ_j the factors (independent variables) and α is the error.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the adsorbent :

Table 2 indicates different physical characteristics of

Table 1. Independent variables : coded and real value in center composite rotatable design

Variables		Symbols levels				
		1.414(- α)	-1	0	+1	1.414(+ α)
Initial concentration (mg/L)	<i>A'</i>	17.982	18.5	19.75	21	21.5178
Adsorbent dosage (g/L)	<i>B'</i>	0.1715	1.0	3.0	5.0	5.83

Table 2. Characteristic of mango leaf powder

Name of adsorbent	Particle size	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Pore volume (cc/g)	Average pore diameter (Å)	BET external surface area (m ² /g)	<i>P</i> _{zc}	Moisture content (Dry basis)	Ash content (Dry basis)
Mango leaf mesh	-44 +52	0.367	0.0042	95.96	2.38	6.82	5.86%	5.21

the mango leaf. The point of zero charge was obtained by solid addition method⁷. The Scanning Electron Micrograph of fresh and loaded with Cr^{VI} mango leaf as shown in Fig. 1(a) and (b), represents the surface morphological characteristics before and after Cr^{VI} adsorption. The observed image at Fig. 1(a) shows high roughness on the adsorbent surface with haphazardly porous in nature. These provides larger effective surface for the easy sorption of Cr^{VI} ions on the adsorbent surface^{4,8,9}. The Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) analysis of the fresh and Cr^{VI} loaded mango leaf is represented in Fig. 2(a) and (b). Fig 2(a) indicates the presence of Ca, O, Mg and Si as natural species on the mango leaf, which could influence the ion-exchange mechanism for adsorption¹⁰ and EDS peaks in Fig. 2(b), demonstrates the existence of Cr^{VI} metals on the surface of the mango leaf.

The findings from the FTIR plot, as shown in Fig. 3, for fresh and Cr^{VI} loaded mango leaves in the range of

4000–400 cm⁻¹, represent the shift in the wave number of dominant peaks. There was shift of wave numbers from 3246.32 to 3310.95, 2916.18–2915.53, 2848.18–2847.95, 1228.66–1224.62 and 1031.22 to 1017.09 which indicated the involvements of surface O-H, aliphatic C-H, aldehyde C-H, carboxylic acid and derivatives of O-C stretching and sulphonic acid S=O stretching respectively. These shifts in the wave number indicated that there was metal binding on the surface of the adsorbent⁴. Being a moderately large ion with crystal radius of 0.52 Å, Cr^{VI} fits into the binding sites of the mango leaf having average pore diameter 95.96 Å and binds to several groups present on the surface.

3.2. Analysis of mass transfer models :

3.2.1. External mass transfer analysis :

The mass transfer analysis is carried out by using the

Fig. 1. SEM image of mango leaf : (a) fresh and (b) loaded with Cr^{IV}.

Fig. 2. (a) and (b) EDS images of fresh and Cr^{VI} loaded mango leaf.

Fig. 3. FTIR analysis for fresh and Cr^{VI} loaded mango leaf.

following equation¹¹.

$$\ln \left(\frac{C_t}{C_0} - \frac{1}{1 + MK_{bq}} \right) = \ln \left(\frac{MK_{bq}}{1 + MK_{bq}} - \frac{1 + MK_{bq}}{MK_{bq}} \right) \beta S_s t \quad (2)$$

The plot of $\ln \left(\frac{C_t}{C_0} - \frac{1}{1 + MK_{bq}} \right)$ versus t yields a straight line with slope $\left(\frac{1 + MK_{bq}}{MK_{bq}} \right) \beta S_s$ and the external mass transfer coefficient β may be calculated from the slopes.

3.2.2. Intra-particle diffusion model :

To describe the diffusion process of Cr^{VI} ions on the microspheres, Fick's equation is attempted⁴ and is expressed as,

$$\frac{q_t}{q_\infty} = \frac{6}{R_a} \sqrt{\frac{D_e t}{\pi}} \quad (3)$$

q_∞ is to replace by q_e . The plot of q_t/q_e vs $t^{0.5}$ of experimental data shows multi-linear segments. External diffusion mass transfer is indicated in the first linear part and the second linear part is indicative of intra-particle diffusion domination in that part⁴. The last linear portion is related to adsorption-desorption equilibrium. The relative time taken by external to intra-particle diffusion shows the influence of each step and helps to determine the rate controlling step.

3.2.3. Urano and Tachikawa [U & T] model :

Another model for intra-particle diffusion was proposed by Urano and Tachikawa¹². In this model the external diffusion is considered negligible and the sorption rate is considered independent of stirring speed. The model is represented by,

$$f\left(\frac{q}{q_m}\right) = -\left[\log\left(1 - \left(\frac{q}{q_m}\right)^2\right)\right] = \frac{4\pi^2 D_i t}{2.3d_p^2} \quad (4)$$

q_m is replaced by q_e and D_i is calculated by linearization at the initial time period of contact.

3.3. Effects of operating parameters on mass transfer :

3.3.1. Effect of pH :

The aqueous phase pH influences the metal adsorption chemistry. To show the effect of pH, experiments were conducted at 4 different pH, ranging from 1 to 6, i.e. below p_{pzc} of 6.82, at a Cr^{VI} concentration of 20 mg L⁻¹ and at 30 °C. 0.1 N H₂SO₄ or 0.1 N NaOH as per requirement was used to monitor the pH of the solution. In aqueous solutions, chromium forms anions like, HCrO₄⁻³, Cr₂O₇²⁻ and CrO₄⁴⁻ and their relative presence depends upon the concentration and pH of the solution¹³. At pH ≤ 1.0, the dominant form of Cr^{VI} is HCrO₄⁻ and increase in pH shifts the concentration of HCrO₄⁻ to Cr₂O₇²⁻ and CrO₄⁴⁻ (Ref. 14). At low pH, a large number of H⁺ ions

are present, which neutralizes the OH⁻ ions on the adsorbent surface and facilitating diffusion and adsorption of negatively charged Cr^{VI} ions on the adsorbent surface⁸. High removal efficiency was noted at pH 1 and 2. Above pH 2, the removal percentage falls sharply and reaches to 43.1% at pH 6 from 99.7% at pH 1. At a pH higher than 6.82, the overall surface charge on the mango leaf become negative and hence adsorption decreases due to the formation of complex of anions which adsorbed on the adsorption surface¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The same trend was also reported by other researchers^{4,8,9,18,19}. The following equilibrium exist for Cr^{VI} anions in aqueous solutions,

Apart from ionic attraction, the external and internal diffusion mass transfer also plays an important role in determination of rate controlling step. The effects of pH on external diffusion is shown in the plot of

$\ln\left(\frac{C_t}{C_0} - \frac{1}{1 + MK_{bq}}\right)$ versus t and depicted in Fig. 4. Table

3 shows that the external film mass transfer coefficient decreases with increase in pH of the aqueous solution.

Fig. 4. Effect of aqueous phase pH on the sorption kinetics of Cr^{VI} ions by mango leaf on external mass transfer diffusion.

With decrease in pH, the attraction between the adsorbate and the adsorbent molecules increases due to higher protonation and this yielded increase in diffusion mass transfer.

The plot of q_t/q_e vs $t^{0.5}$ of experimental data for initial Cr^{VI} concentration of 20 mg L^{-1} and adsorbent dose of 2 g L^{-1} , at varied pH is shown in Fig. 5. Fig. 6 shows the plot of intra-particle diffusion model predicted by Urano and Tachikawa. The diffusion coefficients were evaluated from intra-particle diffusion model of Ficks and the U & T model are presented in Table 3. It was noticed that the values of diffusion coefficients increase with decrease in pH value. This study helped in designing the appropriate pH to achieve maximum efficiency for removal of Cr^{VI} by mango leaf powder. In future studies, the aqueous solution pH was maintained at 2.0 to get the optimum adsorption.

3.3.2. Effect of adsorbent concentration :

The effects of variation of adsorbent dose on external mass transfer coefficients and internal mass transfer coefficients were calculated from the above models Eqs.(2-4) are presented in Table 3. It may be seen that the both the external and intra-particle diffusion coefficients, calculated from the models, increase with increase in sorbent concentration. Fig. 7 shows that Cr^{VI} removal increased at a very fast rate with the increase in adsorbent concentration and reaches to 99.58%. It may be explained that with increase in adsorbent dose, more surface area was available for adsorption so the removal efficiency increased but the adsorption capacity (mg g^{-1}) decreased, because of increase in sorbent quantity. The mango leaf concentration of 2 g L^{-1} seems to be optimum and thereafter the removal efficiency did not increase significantly. Since optimum removal efficiency was found at an adsorbent

Table 3. Values of diffusion coefficients and mass transfer coefficients

Parameters	External film mass transfer coefficient, based on McKay model $\beta_L \times 10^5 \text{ (cm s}^{-1}\text{)}$	R^2	Effective diffusion coefficient based on Fick's equation $D_e \times 10^8 \text{ (cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$	R^2	Intraparticle diffusion coefficient for U & T model $D_i \times 10^8 \text{ (cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$	R^2
Effect of pH						
1	4.44	0.9843	1.92	0.9415	3.78	0.9772
2	1.50	0.9922	0.74	0.9248	0.85	0.9875
4	0.07	0.5403	0.51	0.8793	0.27	0.8625
6	0.06	0.7002	0.20	0.8568	0.11	0.8853
Effect of adsorbent dose (g L^{-1})						
0.5	0.16	0.9851	0.12	0.9770	0.17	0.8743
1.0	0.39	0.9838	0.31	0.9391	0.28	0.9867
2.0	1.50	0.9926	0.74	0.9248	0.85	0.9905
3.0	3.27	0.9517	1.51	0.9469	1.57	0.9639
5.0	2.88	0.8022	5.71	0.8374	5.40	0.8956
10.0	8.82	0.9548	5.28	0.9497	8.45	0.9479
Effect of initial Cr^{VI} concentration (mg L^{-1})						
20	1.50	0.9927	0.74	0.9573	0.85	0.9905
40	0.46	0.9856	0.44	0.9248	0.53	0.9679
60	0.29	0.9794	0.41	0.9675	0.28	0.9698
80	0.20	0.9537	0.29	0.9556	0.37	0.9480
100	0.16	0.9333	0.23	0.9449	0.31	0.9394
Effect of particle size (μm)						
575	0.66	0.9795	0.63	0.9856	0.51	0.9934
325	1.49	0.9936	0.74	0.9248	0.85	0.9905
270	1.28	0.9717	0.90	0.9842	0.88	0.9928

Fig. 5. Effect of aqueous phase pH on the sorption kinetics of Cr^{VI} ions by mango leaf on intra-particle mass transfer diffusion model by Ficks.

Fig. 6. Effect of aqueous phase pH on the sorption kinetics of Cr^{VI} ions by mango leaf on intra-particle mass transfer diffusion model by Urano and Tachikawa.

concentration of 2 g L⁻¹, it was maintained for rest of the experiments. This reduces the usages of adsorbent quantity and hence more economical.

Fig. 7. Effect of adsorbent dose on the sorption kinetics of Cr^{VI} ions by mango leaf on Cr^{VI} removal percentage.

3.3.3. Effect of initial metal ion concentration :

Fig. 8 shows variation of normalized concentration of Cr^{VI} with time at different initial Cr^{VI} concentrations at 30 °C. Removal of Cr^{VI} drops to 69.27% at a concentration level of 100 mg L⁻¹ from 99.23% at 20 mg L⁻¹ at 30 °C. The possible reason may be that at lower concentration level adsorption takes place at higher active sites of the adsorbent and as concentration of metal ion increases, adsorption is to take place at lower active sites and thus adsorption decreases⁸. The external film mass transfer coefficient and the intra-particle diffusion coefficients calculated from the plots of Eqs. (2-4), decreased with increasing initial Cr^{VI} concentrations as may be seen from Table 3. Increasing metal concentration in the solution reduced the diffusion of metal ions in the boundary and in the pores. The results are consistent with other researchers²⁰.

3.3.4. Effect of particle size :

The effect of particle size on external diffusion is provided in Fig. 9 and the mass transfer coefficients evaluated and presented in Table 3. The adsorption yield was high at lower particle sizes due to increase in surface area per unit mass for smaller particle size. Table 3 shows that

Fig. 8. Effect of initial Cr^{VI} concentrations on the sorption kinetics of Cr^{VI} ions by mango leaf on normalized Cr^{VI} concentration.

Fig. 9. Effect of particle size on the sorption kinetics of Cr^{VI} ions by mango leaf effect on external mass transfer diffusion model.

the external film mass transfer coefficient decreases with increase in particle size of the adsorbent. The decrease in

particle size decreased both external mass transfer resistance and intra-particle diffusion resistance. The plot of q_t/q_e vs $t^{0.5}$ of experimental data for initial Cr^{VI} concentration of 20 mg L⁻¹ at an adsorbent dose of 2 g L⁻¹ and pH 2, is shown in Fig. 10. The time taken by the multi-linear segments was calculated and the ratio of time taken for external diffusion to intra-particle diffusion was 1 : 2.75, 1 : 2.82 and 1 : 4.18 for particle sizes 270, 325 and 575 μm respectively. So, it is concluded that the intra-particle diffusion might be the rate controlling step. Fig. 11 shows the plot of model predicted by Urano and Tachikawa. The diffusion coefficients were evaluated and reported in Table 3.

Fig. 10. Effect of particle size on the sorption kinetics of Cr^{VI} ions by mango leaf on intra-particle mass transfer diffusion model by Ficks.

3.4.5. Effect of contact time :

Time has an important role in metal adsorption and sufficient time of 240 min was allowed for each experiments to reach equilibrium. Adsorption increased with time and after some time the rate became constant. The effect of contact time on batch adsorption of at three different temperatures is shown in Fig. 12 for initial Cr^{VI} concentration of 20 mg L⁻¹ and adsorbent dose of 2 g L⁻¹

Fig. 11. Effect of particle size on the sorption kinetics of Cr^{VI} ions by mango leaf on intra-particle mass transfer diffusion model predicted by Urano and Tachikawa.

Fig. 12. Effect of temperature on the sorption kinetics of Cr^{VI} ions by mango leaf on removal percentage.

and at pH 2. 90% adsorption was completed within 1 h. Thereafter, the reaction rate became very slow and reaches equilibrium in nearly three hours.

3.4.6. Effect of temperature :

The influence of temperature on biosorption of Cr^{VI} conducted at three temperatures ranging from 30–50 °C. Fig. 13 displays that the equilibrium adsorption capacity, q_e , of Cr^{VI} is increased with increase in initial Cr^{VI} concentration and further increases with increase in temperature. The experimental values of q_e , increased from

Fig. 13. Variation of equilibrium adsorption capacity (q_e) with Cr^{VI} concentration and temperature.

9.91 to 35.08 mg g⁻¹ at 30 °C and from 10.09 to 39.41 mg g⁻¹ at 50 °C as concentration increased from 20 to 100 mg L⁻¹. The biosorption efficiency and the metal uptake increased with temperature. External and internal diffusion rate increased with increasing temperature. This effect is suggestive of formation of chemical bond or chemical reaction in the sorption process²¹. 80.46% removal was noticed at 50 °C at a concentration of 100 mg L⁻¹. Table 4 shows that the external mass transfer coefficients increased with increase in temperature. Further, the internal diffusion coefficients also increased. The increase in yield and adsorption capacity at higher temperatures, indicates that the adsorption is not only physical but chemisorptions may also be involved and the process is endothermic in nature²².

Table 4. Effect of temperature at different concentrations

On external mass transfer coefficient						
Initial concn. (mg L ⁻¹)	External film mass transfer coefficient, $\beta_L \times 10^5$ (cm s ⁻¹)			R^2		
	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C
20	1.50	1.95	2.04	0.9927	0.9933	0.9790
40	0.46	0.52	0.81	0.9856	0.9665	0.9033
60	0.29	0.24	0.37	0.9794	0.9754	0.9602
80	0.20	0.17	0.22	0.9537	0.9136	0.9571
100	0.16	0.16	0.17	0.9333	0.9496	0.9263
On internal diffusion rate parameter						
Initial concn. (mg L ⁻¹)	Internal diffusion coefficient, $D_e \times 10^8$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)			R^2		
	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C
20	0.74	1.09	1.62	0.9573	0.9514	0.9808
40	0.44	0.50	0.63	0.9248	0.9098	0.9828
60	0.41	0.38	0.55	0.9675	0.9777	0.9897
80	0.29	0.32	0.33	0.9556	0.9765	0.9248
100	0.23	0.23	0.32	0.9449	0.9325	0.9536
On intra-particle diffusion co-efficient						
Initial concn. (mg L ⁻¹)	Intra-particle diffusion coefficient of U & T Model, $D_i \times 10^8$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)			R^2		
	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C
20	0.85	1.40	2.21	0.9905	0.9969	0.9945
40	0.53	0.59	0.76	0.9679	0.9844	0.9806
60	0.28	0.34	0.57	0.9698	0.9571	0.9936
80	0.37	0.54	0.32	0.9480	0.9839	0.9247
100	0.31	0.37	0.43	0.9394	0.9501	0.9767

3.5. Investigation of sorption kinetics :

Adsorption kinetic models :

Kinetics is an important factor for describing the residence time required for solid uptake at the solid-liquid interface. The rate depends upon the physical and chemical characteristics of the adsorbents and on the mass transfer process^{4,9}. The following kinetic models are attempted to predict the order of the reaction.

3.5.1. The Lagergren pseudo 1st order model :

This model²³ is expressed as,

$$\log (q_e - q) = \log q_e - \frac{k_1 t}{2.303} \quad (8)$$

The rate constants and the equilibrium adsorption capaci-

ties at three different temperatures for pseudo 1st order reaction were obtained from the plot of $\log (q_e - q)$ versus t as displayed in Fig. 14 and the parameters are presented in Table 5 with statistical analysis. It may be seen that the rate constants decrease with increase in concentration whereas increases with increase in temperature.

3.5.2. The pseudo second order model :

The model²⁴ assumes that chemisorptions takes place on the adsorbent surface. The linear form of pseudo second order Equation is expressed by

$$\frac{t}{q} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{1}{q_e} \quad (9)$$

The pseudo second order parameters were determined

Fig. 14. Lagergren plot for different temperatures.

from the plot of t/q vs t at different initial Cr^{VI} concentrations (Fig. 15) and the values are reported in Table 5. By comparing the correlation coefficients, obtained from both the models, it may be concluded that the pseudo second order model fits the experimental data well. This means

Fig. 15. Pseudo second order plot.

that the chemical interaction between the adsorbent sites and Cr^{VI} ions might have taken place²⁵. Moreover, the pseudo second order rate constant increases with temperature while decreases with increasing concentration.

3.5.3. Elovich model :

Elovich model was basically for chemical adsorption of gases on solid surface without desorption of the products, so the rate of adsorption decreases with time due to surface coverage. The model is applicable in case of chemisorptions. The simplified form of the model is given by Srivastava *et al.*⁷,

$$q_t = \left(\frac{1}{b_1}\right) \ln (a_1 b_1) + \left(\frac{1}{b_1}\right) \ln t \quad (10)$$

The model kinetic parameters were evaluated from the plot of $\ln t$ vs q_t and shown at Table 5 along with the correlation coefficients. The experimental data fitted reasonably well with the model and that are indications of chemisorptions.

The sorption kinetics was studied by using the external mass transfer diffusion model and intra-particle diffusion models. The value of mass transfer coefficient (β) was calculated for all process variables and depicted at Table 4. The values of mass transfer coefficients indicate that the mass transfer was quite fast. In this analysis it is assumed that initially the concentration of Cr^{VI} is zero on the surface of the adsorbent and interparticle diffusion is negligible. The change in adsorbate concentration with time is due to solid-liquid mass transfer only²⁰.

3.6. Equilibrium sorption models :

Adsorption isotherms indicate the qualitative information on the nature of the solute surface interaction and also relation between the concentration of adsorbate and its degree of accumulation onto adsorbent surface. Adsorption isotherms are used to optimize the use of adsorbents and the analysis of the isotherm data fitting them to different isotherm models is an important step to find the suitable model which can be used for scale-up design^{7,26}.

The equilibrium studies were conducted varying initial Cr^{VI} ion concentration from 20 to 100 mg L^{-1} at 30–50 °C at adsorbent dose level of 2 g L^{-1} . The adsorption equilibrium data are represented by the following isotherm models.

Table 5. Kinetic model parameters

1st Order kinetic model parameters									
Initial Cr ^{VI} concn. (mg L ⁻¹)	First order rate constant, $k_1 \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)			q_e (mg/g)			R^2		
	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C
20	36.32	64.48	121.75	8.21	9.48	13.99	0.9975	0.9833	0.8732
40	18.49	39.84	35.99	16.07	26.74	19.04	0.9823	0.8757	0.9825
60	15.94	24.503	20.10	22.72	30.51	22.83	0.9872	0.7283	0.9832
80	15.82	16.12	12.59	26.73	24.34	27.40	0.9680	0.9775	0.9874
100	13.22	12.47	12.73	28.02	44.04	30.81	0.9894	0.7165	0.9798
2nd Order kinetic model parameters									
Initial Cr ^{VI} concn. (mg L ⁻¹)	Second order rate constants, $k_2 \times 10^3$ (mg/g/min)			q_e (mg/g)			R^2		
	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C
20	6.38	11.83	17.36	10.98	10.95	10.53	0.9943	0.9984	0.9638
40	2.22	2.51	3.87	20.79	22.67	23.69	0.9949	0.9957	0.9968
60	1.34	1.22	1.88	27.78	28.80	30.88	0.9841	0.9886	0.9948
80	1.12	1.05	0.55	32.78	32.10	35.92	0.9887	0.9942	0.9747
100	1.10	1.01	0.918	36.76	37.41	41.56	0.9869	0.9782	0.9428
Elovich model parameters									
Initial Cr ^{VI} concn. (mg L ⁻¹)	a_1 , Elovich constant			b_1			R^2		
	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C
20	1.78	2.90	5.11	0.46	0.46	0.45	0.9833	0.9776	0.9631
40	2.82	3.83	4.79	0.27	0.28	0.23	0.9710	0.9822	0.9872
60	2.69	2.78	4.97	0.21	0.24	0.18	0.9362	0.9539	0.9893
80	3.62	4.34	5.30	0.19	0.21	0.19	0.9493	0.9797	0.9592
100	4.59	9.03	4.55	0.17	0.25	0.14	0.9243	0.9320	0.9598

3.6.1. Langmuir isotherm model :

The Langmuir²⁷ model assumes monolayer adsorption with a finite number of adsorption sites. The model is expressed by :

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{C_e}{q_{\max}} + \frac{1}{q_{\max}b} \quad (11)$$

The essential characteristics of Langmuir isotherm may be expressed in terms of a dimensionless constant, called separation factor⁴, R_L , which is defined as,

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + bC_0} \quad (12)$$

The R_L value lying between 0 and 1 indicates strong affinity for adsorption. From the slope and intercept of the linear plot of $\frac{C_e}{q_e}$ vs C_e of Langmuir model, the values of q_{\max} and b were evaluated and reported in Table 6. The maximum adsorption capacity was 31.02 at 30 °C and 39.65 at 50 °C. The linearity and high correlation coefficient (0.9918–0.9952) indicated favorable application of the model.

3.6.2. Freundlich isotherm model :

This model²⁸ assumes that adsorbent had a heterogeneous surface composed of different classes of adsorption sites and is represented by

Table 6. Isotherm model parameters

Langmuir isotherm model : $\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{C_e}{q_{\max}} + \frac{1}{q_{\max}b}$					
Separation factor, $R_L = \frac{1}{1 + bC_0}$					
Temp. (°C)	q_{\max} (mg/g)	b (L/mg)	R^2	At initial concentration of 20 mg L ⁻¹	At final concentration of 100 mg L ⁻¹
30	31.02	1.2977	0.9918	0.0676	0.0076
40	34.33	1.4000	0.9839	0.0332	0.0075
50	39.65	2.3650	0.9952	0.0205	0.0043
Freundlich isotherm model : $\log q_e = \log K_f + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e$					
Temp. (°C)	K_f (mg/g)/(mg/L) ^{1/n}	n	R^2		
30	14.17	3.6056	0.9573		
40	20.63	6.3584	0.7723		
50	25.70	6.2293	0.9083		
Temkin isotherm model : $q_e = B \ln A_T + B \ln C_e$; $B = \frac{RT}{b_T}$					
Temp. (°C)	B (J/mol)	A_T (L/mg)	b_T	R^2	
30	87.03	1.00	28.94	0.9696	
40	62.68	1.01	41.51	0.8579	
50	67.08	1.012	40.03	0.9789	
Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm model : $\ln C_{\text{abs}} = \ln X_m - \lambda \varepsilon^2$; $\varepsilon = RT \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{C_e} \right)$; $E = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\lambda}}$					
Temp. (°C)	E (kJ/mol)	X_m (mmol/g)	R^2		
30	9.53	0.61	0.9496		
40	12.5	0.64	0.8244		
50	14.74	0.73	0.9676		

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad (13)$$

where, n , is an empirical parameter related to adsorption intensity and varies with degree of heterogeneity. For favorable adsorption, n should be between 1-10 Malkoc *et al.*¹⁹. From the plot of Freundlich model, the model parameters were calculated are reported in Table 6. Table 6 indicates that statistical parameters of Langmuir model fitted better than the Freundlich model. This indicates that the adsorption occurs on the homogeneous surface by monolayer adsorption and described by chemisorptions due to formation of ionic or covalent bonds between the adsorbents and adsorbate²⁹.

3.6.3. Temkin isotherm model :

The model is used to predict the adsorption potential of the adsorbent and is based on assumptions that the heat of adsorption would decrease linearly with the increase of coverage of adsorbent due to adsorbate-adsorbent interactions¹⁶. Temkin model is represented by

$$q_e = B \ln A_T + B \ln C_e; B = \frac{RT}{b_T} \quad (14)$$

From the plot of q_e versus $\ln C_e$, Temkin model constant, b_T , was obtained from the slope and the Temkin isotherm constant, A_T , was obtained from the intercept. The values are presented at Table 6.

3.6.4. Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm model :

This model³⁰ is used to estimate the characteristic porosity of the biomass and the apparent energy of adsorption³¹. The nature of adsorption process may be predicted by this model. The linear form of model is described by

$$\ln C_{\text{abs}} = \ln X_m - \lambda \varepsilon^2 \quad (15)$$

where, the Polanyi potential, ε , is given by,

$$\varepsilon = RT \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{C_e} \right) \quad (16)$$

From the plot of q_e vs ε^2 , the values of λ and X_m are calculated from slope and intercept respectively. The mean sorption energy, E , was evaluated from

$$E = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\lambda}} \quad (17)$$

The calculated value of the sorption energy, E (kJ/mol), gives an information about the nature of adsorption process, whether physical or chemical. If the value of E is less than 8 kJ/mol, the process is physical adsorption and the values between 8 to 16 kJ/mol the process is chemisorptions^{4,32}. Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm model parameters were determined from the plot of $\ln C_{\text{abs}}$ vs ε^2 , λ and X_m were calculated from slope and intercept respectively. The mean sorption energy, E was evaluated from Eq. (17) and reported in Table 6. The estimated value of sorption energy varied from 9.53 to 14.74 kJ/mol, indicated the process was chemisorptions.

3.7. Thermodynamic study :

The thermodynamic parameters, such as Gibbs free energy (ΔG^0), enthalpy (ΔH^0) and entropy (ΔS^0) on adsorption of Cr^{VI} on mango leaf powder were determined by using the following equations,

$$K'_C = \frac{C_{\text{ad, eq}}}{C_{\text{eq}}} \quad (18)$$

$$\Delta G^0 = -RT \ln K'_C \quad (19)$$

$$\ln K'_C = \frac{\Delta H^0}{RT} - \frac{\Delta S^0}{R} \quad (20)$$

Experiments were conducted to see the effects of temperature, at a range of 30–50 °C, varying initial Cr^{VI}

concentration from 20 to 100 mg L⁻¹ and adsorbent dose level of 2 g L⁻¹. The heterogeneous equilibrium was established between the Cr^{VI} in the solution and Cr^{VI} on the adsorbent. The apparent equilibrium constant, K'_C was calculated by Eq. (18) at different initial concentrations and then extrapolating to zero to get K'_C^0 . The Gibbs free energy (ΔG^0) is calculated from Eq. (19) and is presented in Table 7. The negative value of free energy suggests that the adsorption process is spontaneous and its further decrease with temperature increase indicates that the spontaneity increases with increase in temperature. The enthalpy (ΔH^0) and entropy was calculated from the slope and the intercept of the plot of $\ln K'_C^0$ vs $1/T$ and shown in Fig. 16.

The calculated enthalpy was 88.19 kJ/mol and entropy was 0.334 kJ/mol.K. Positive values of enthalpy and entropy change suggest the adsorption process was endot-

Table 7. Thermodynamic parameters

Metal ion	ΔH^0 (kJ/mol)	ΔS^0 (kJ/mol)	T (K)	$-\Delta G^0$ (kJ/mol)	R^2
Cr^{IV}	88.19	0.334	303	12.58	0.9121
			313	15.79	
			323	20.44	

Fig. 16. Plot of $\ln K'_C^0$ vs $1/T$.

hermic and the random in nature. Moreover, the value of enthalpy change suggests that the adsorption of Cr^{VI} on mango leaf was chemisorptions in nature as it lies between 20–200 kJ/mol³³.

3.8. Single-stage batch adsorption system design :

The mass balance Eq. for adsorption of Cr^{VI} on the adsorbent surface from the aqueous solution at any point of time, may be written as

$$V(C_0 - C_t) = W(q_t - q_0) \quad (21)$$

If fresh adsorbents are used, $q_0 = 0$, so the Eq. (21) reduces to,

$$V(C_0 - C_t) = Wq_t \quad (22)$$

When the system reaches equilibrium, the Eq. may be rewritten as :

$$V(C_0 - C_e) = Wq_e \quad (23)$$

Since, the adsorption systems followed Langmuir adsorption isotherm relationship better, the Langmuir model is followed for designing of the batch adsorption system. The Langmuir equilibrium relationship is given by Eq. (11) and combining Eqs. (23) and (11), we get,

$$\frac{W}{V} = \frac{(C_0 - C_e)(bC_e + 1)}{bC_e q_{\max}} \quad (24)$$

From the known values of b and q_{\max} , the Eq. (24) is further simplified and a relationship for W/V is obtained in terms of C_0 and C_e . Fig. 17 shows the plot of mass of mango leaf powder required for removal of Cr^{VI} for aqueous solution containing 50 mg/L Cr^{VI} ion for 70%, 80% and 90% removal at different volume of solutions (1–10 L).

3.9. Safe disposal of the Cr^{VI} loaded adsorbent :

To prevent leaching of Cr^{VI} ions, direct disposal of Cr^{VI} loaded adsorbents are not recommended. The loaded adsorbent was incinerated at 700 °C and then the leaching tests of the ash were conducted^{9,34}. It was observed that Cr^{VI} did not leach from the ash sample. So this ash may be used for land filling.

3.10. Statistical analysis :

In the present work, the relationship between response

Fig. 17. Plot of mass of mango leaf required for removal of Cr^{VI} for aqueous solution.

(removal % and adsorption capacity, mg/g) and two independent factors (initial concentration and adsorbent dosage) were studied. The results at each point are based on the experimental design are shown in Table 8 and Table 9. The experimental sequence was randomized in order to minimize the effects of the uncontrolled factors.

Regression analysis is the general approach to fit the empirical model with the collected response variable data. By using multiple regression analysis, the response obtained in Tables 8 and 9 was correlated with the two independent factors using the polynomial equation as in Eq. (1). The coefficients of the full regression model Eq. and their statistical significance were determined and evaluated using Design-Expert 7.0 software from State-Ease Inc. The final model in terms of actual value is :

$$Y = 92.17 - 5.30A' + 16.64B' + 5.75A'B' + 1.12A'^2 - 10.61B'^2 \quad (25)$$

Positive sign in front of the terms indicates synergistic effect, while negative sign indicates antagonistic effect. The results obtained were then analyzed by ANOVA to assess the goodness of fit. The significant quadratic models, linear model and the corresponding significant model

Table 8. Experimental design results for adsorption of Cr^{VI} using mango leaf

Run	Factors		Response	Response
	Initial concentration- mg/L (<i>A'</i>)	Adsorbent dosage g/L (<i>B'</i>)	(% of removal) experimental	(% of removal) predicted
1	18.5	1.0	79.14	77.08
2	18.5	5.0	99.99	98.88
3	19.75	3.0	90.87	92.17
4	19.75	5.83	94.87	94.49
5	21.00	5.0	98.3	99.77
6	19.75	3.0	87.64	92.17
7	19.75	0.17	46.46	47.42
8	19.75	3.0	89.45	92.17
9	21.52	3.0	88.45	86.91
10	19.75	3.0	94.65	92.17
11	19.75	3.0	98.24	92.17
12	17.98	3.0	99.78	100.00
13	21.00	1.0	54.46	54.99

Table 9. Experimental design results for adsorption of Cr^{VI} using mango leaf

Run	Factors		Response	Response
	Initial concentration mg/L (<i>A'</i>)	Adsorbent dosage g/L (<i>B'</i>)	(Adsorption capacity, mg/g) experimental	(Adsorption capacity, mg/g) predicted
1	18.5	1.0	8.8	8.58
2	18.5	5.0	3.45	4.08
3	19.75	3.0	7.01	6.31
4	19.75	5.83	4	3.13
5	21.00	5.0	3.94	4.03
6	19.75	3.0	5.7	6.31
7	19.75	0.17	9.01	9.49
8	19.75	3.0	5	6.31
9	21.52	3.0	5.88	6.27
10	19.75	3.0	6.85	6.31
11	19.75	3.0	6	6.31
12	17.98	3.0	9.01	9.49
13	21.00	1.0	9.5	8.53

term for all responses are tabulated in Tables 10 and 11. It is seen that probability (*P*) value of the model term is less than 0.05 which relies the model is significant and adequate for predicting the Cr^{VI} removal percentage yield within the range of the variables studied.

From Table 11, it is also observed that adsorbent dos-

age (*B'*) has a larger effect than initial concentration (*A'*) of Cr^{VI} ion on the Cr^{VI} removal yield significantly due to the high F-value. The quadratic term of than adsorbent dosage (*B'²*), F-value 61.94 is more significant than the initial feed concentration (*A'²*), F-value 0.69. Besides that, the effect of interaction between initial feed concentration and adsorbent dosage (*A'B'*), also affect the Cr^{VI} removal yield significantly (F-value 10.45).

To test the fit of the model, the regression Eq. and determination coefficient (*R*²) were evaluated. In this case, the value of the determination coefficient (*R*² = 0.9946) indicates that the sample variation of 99.46% for Cr^{VI} removal yield is attributed to the independent variables and only 0.54% of the total variations are not explained by the model. The value of the adjusted determination coefficient (Adj. *R*² = 0.9965) is also very high to advocate for a high significance of the model. A higher value of the correlation coefficient justifies an excellent correlation between the independent variables³⁵.

On the other hand, a relatively lower value of the coefficient of variation (*CV* = 0.04%) indicates a better precision and reliability of the experiments carried out³⁶. The *CV* as the ratio of the standard error of estimate to the mean value of the observed response (as a percentage) is a measure of reproducibility of the model and as a general rule a model can be considered reasonably reproducible if its *CV* is not greater than 10%³⁷. By applying diagnostic plots including normal probability plot of residual, plot of residuals versus predicted, the assumptions of normality, independence and randomness of the residual were satisfied. The fitted model for yield of Cr^{VI} removal was accepted.

The response surface 3D plot is demonstrated in Fig. 18. Initial Cr^{VI} ion concentration and adsorbent dosages are the most important parameters that can be the impression the adsorption efficiency. Fig. 18 also shows the simultaneous effects of percentage removal and initial ion concentrations on the metal ion adsorption efficiency. In this figure, the removal efficiency improved with increasing adsorbent dosage due to increase in available binding sites for interactions.

Table 10. ANOVA for response surface quadratic model for percentage removal

Source	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean of square	F Value	Prob > F	Remarks
Model	3399.90	5	679.98	53.82	< 0.0001	Significant
<i>A'</i>	224.65	1	224.65	17.78	0.0040	Significant
<i>B'</i>	2216.18	1	2216.18	175.40	< 0.0001	Significant
<i>A'B'</i>	132.14	1	132.14	10.45	0.0144	Significant
<i>A'²</i>	8.70	1	8.70	0.69	0.4341	
<i>B'²</i>	782.65	1	782.65	61.94	0.0001	Significant
Residual	88.44	7	12.63			
Lack of fit	15.84	3	5.28	0.29	0.8309	Not significant
Pure error	72.60	4	18.15			

Table 11. ANOVA for Response Surface Linear Model for adsorption capacity

Source	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean of square	F Value	Prob > F	Remarks
Model	40.48	2	20.24	35.09	< 0.0001	Significant
<i>A'</i>	4.799E-003	1	4.799E-003	8.318E-003	0.9291	
<i>B'</i>	40.48	1	40.48	70.17	< 0.0001	Significant
Residual	5.77	10	0.58			
Lack of fit	3.00	6	0.50	0.72	0.6571	Not significant
Pure error	2.77	4	0.69			

Fig. 18. Response surface 3D plot of interaction between Cr^{VI} ion concentration and percentage removal and between Cr^{VI} ion initial concentration and adsorbent dosage.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrated the potential of using dry mango leaf, a natural waste for Cr^{VI} removal from aqueous solution. A series of batch experiments were done for removal of Cr^{VI} from aqueous solution at different process parameters, like pH, adsorbent dose, initial Cr^{VI}

concentration, contact time, particle size and temperature. The results may be summarized as follows :

- (i) The removal of Cr^{VI} from aqueous solution was influenced by parameters such as aqueous phase pH, adsorbent dose, initial Cr^{VI} concentration, particle size and temperature. The influence was noticed for both kinetics

and equilibrium studies.

(ii) Adsorption strongly depends upon pH of the solution and the maximum removal efficiency was noted at pH 2.

(iii) The point of zero charge on the adsorbent surface was 6.82.

(iv) Almost 100% removal of Cr^{VI} was possible for 20 mg L⁻¹ solution at an adsorbent dose of 2 g L⁻¹ and pH 2. Higher adsorption was noted at high temperatures.

(v) A good correlation of experimental data with the external and internal mass transfer diffusion models indicated that the sorption process was dominated by diffusion mechanism. These findings reflected for all process parameters as indicated by high correlation coefficients (0.8625–0.9936). Considering the size of Cr^{VI} ions and the average pore diameter of the mango leaf powder, it may be concluded that no hindrances was faced by Cr^{VI} ions for pore diffusion.

(vi) Decrease in particle size yielded higher diffusion coefficients for both external and internal diffusions due to increase in active surface area.

(vii) Both external and internal diffusion mass transfer coefficient increased temperature but decreased with increase in initial Cr^{VI} concentration.

(viii) The intra-particle diffusion was the rate controlling step.

(ix) The kinetic process was best described by the pseudo second order model with correlation coefficient 0.9949. Elovich model also reflected well with experimental data which are indications of chemisorptions.

(x) Langmuir and Temkin adsorption isotherm was better fitted than Freundlich model, which indicates that the monolayer and chemical adsorptions took place.

(xi) Sorption energy calculated from Dubini-Radushkevich model suggests chemisorption.

(xii) Thermodynamic parameters show that the adsorption was spontaneous and endothermic in nature.

(xiii) FTIR studies indicated that the surface O-H, aliphatic C-H, aldehyde C-H, carboxylic acid and derivatives O-C and sulphonic S=O stretchings were responsible for adsorption.

(xiv) Application of RSM in the process optimization

and modelling facilitated the analysis of interaction effects of the process variables on the response. The maximum Cr^{VI} removal yield of 99% was achieved at 18.5 mg L⁻¹ initial feed concentration with adsorbent dosage around 5 g L⁻¹.

(xv) The study suggests the use of mango leaf as a potential low-cost, natural and abundant source adsorbent for removal of Cr^{VI} from aqueous solution.

Nomenclature

a_1	Elovich constant which gives an idea about rate constant
A_T	Temkin isotherm equilibrium binding constant (L/g)
A'	RSM Variable for initial concentration
b	Langmuir constant (L/mg)
b_1	Elovich constant which represents the rate of chemisorptions at zero coverage
b_T	Temkin constant related to heat of sorption (J/mol)
B	Temkin constant related to heat of sorption (J/mol)
B'	RSM variable for adsorbent dosage
C_{abs}	The amount of Cr ^{VI} adsorbed onto adsorbent surface (mol/g)
C_e	Metal ion concentration at equilibrium in liquid (mg/L)
C_0	Influent metal ion concentration at $t = 0$ (mg/L)
C_t	Effluent metal ion concentration at time t (mg/L)
C_t/C_0	Normalized concentration (dimensionless)
D_e	Effective diffusion coefficient of absorbate in the absorbent phase (cm ² /s)
D_i	Intra-particle diffusion coefficient of absorbate in the absorbent phase (cm ² /s)
d_p	Diameter of the adsorbent particle, cm
E	Sorption energy (kJ/mol)
ΔG^0	Gibbs free energy (kJ/mol)
ΔH^0	Enthalpy (kJ/mol)
ΔS^0	Entropy (kJ/mol.K)

K_1, K_2, K_3	Equilibrium constant	δ_i	Linear coefficient
K_f	Freundlich constant [(mg/g)(L/mg)] ^{1/n}	δ_{ii}	Quadratic coefficient
k_1	Pseudo first order rate constant (min ⁻¹)	δ_{ij}	Interaction effect
k_2	Pseudo second order rate constant (mg/g/min)	α	Error
K_{bq}	The constant obtained by multiplying q_{\max} and b	λ_i, λ_j	Factors (independent variables)

K_c^0	Thermodynamic equilibrium constant
K_c'	Apparent equilibrium constant
M	Mass of the adsorbent per unit volume (g/L)
n	Freundlich constant, intensity of adsorption [(mg/g)/(mg/L)] ^{1/n}
q	Total adsorbed Cr ^{VI} at time t (mg/g)
q_m	Metal uptake by adsorbent after infinite time (mg/g)
q_o	Maximum metal uptake per g of the adsorbent (mg/g)
q_e	Equilibrium metal uptake by adsorbent (mg/g)
q_t	Total adsorbed Cr ^{VI} at time t (mg/g)
q_{to}	Total adsorbed Cr ^{VI} at time $t = 0$ (mg)
q	Metal uptake by adsorbent after infinite time (mg/g)
R^2	Correlation coefficient
R	Ideal gas constant (J/mol/K)
R_L	Separation factor
R_a	Radius of adsorbent particle (cm)
S_s	External surface area of the adsorbent per unit volume (cm ⁻¹)
t	Time (min)
T	Temperature (K)
X_m	Maximum adsorption capacity of adsorbent mmol/g
Y	Response

Greek letters

β	Mass transfer coefficient (cm/s)
ϵ	Polanyi potential
λ	Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm constant (mol ² /kJ ²)
δ	Constant coefficient

6. References

1. M. Cieslak-Golonka, *Polyhedron*, 1996, **15**, 3667.
2. C. Raji and T. S. Anirudhan, *Water Research*, 1998, **32**, 3772.
3. H. Liu, Y. Dong, H. Wang and Y. Liu, *Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 2010, **22**, 1513.
4. B. Singha and S. K. Das, *Colloids and surfaces B : Biointerfaces*, 2011, **84**, 221.
5. R. D. Vidic, M. T. Suidan and R. C. Brenner, *Environmental Science and Technology*, 1993, **27**, 2079.
6. "Standard methods for examination of water and wastewater", 1998, 20th ed., APHA, AWWA, WWF, NW, Washington DC.
7. V. C. Srivastava, I. D. Mall and I. M. Mishra, *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2006, **134**, 257.
8. A. K. Bhattacharya, T. K. Naiya, S. N. Mandal and S. K. Das, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 2008, **137**, 529.
9. S. Nag, A. Mondal, U. Mishra, N. Bar and S. K. Das, *Desalination and Water Treatment*, 2016, **57**, 16927.
10. G. H. N. Pino, L. M. S. de Mesquita, M. L. Torem and G. A. S. Pinto, *Minerals Engineering*, 2006, **19**, 380.
11. G. McKay, M. S. Otterburn and A. G. Sweeney, *Water Research*, 1981, **15**, 327.
12. K. Urano and H. Tachikawa, *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 1991, **30**, 1897.
13. D. Mohan and C. U. Pittman, *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2006, **137**, 762.
14. Y. C. Sharma, *Indian Journal of Chemical Technology*, 2001, **8**, 186.
15. D. Balarak, Y. Mahdavi, F. Gharibi and S. Sadeghi, *Journal of Advances in Environmental Health Research*, 2015, **2**, 234.
16. E. Malkoc, Y. Nuhoglu and Y. K. Abali, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 2006a, **119**, 61.
17. P. Miretzky and A. F. Cirelli, *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2010, **180**, 1.
18. M. Dakiky, M. Khamis, A. Manassra and M. Mer'eb, *Advances in Environmental Research*, 2002, **6**, 533.
19. E. Malkoc, Y. Nuhoglu and M. Dunder, *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2006b, **138**, 142.
20. Y. Sag and Y. Aktay, *Process Biochemistry*, 2000, **36**, 157.

21. Y.-S. Ho and G. McKay, *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, 1998, **76**, 183.
22. K. Srividya and M. Kaustubha, *Journal of Water Resource and Protection*, 2011.
23. S. Lagergren, "About the theory of so-called adsorption of soluble substances", 1898.
24. Ho McKay and Forster Wase, *Adsorption Science & Technology*, 2000, **18**, 639.
25. E. W. Wambu, G. K. Muthakia and P. M. Shiundu, *Bulletin of the Chemical Society of Ethiopia*, 2011, 25.
26. M. M. A. El-Latif, A. M. Ibrahim, M. S. Showman and R. R. A. Hamide, *Int. J. Nonferrous Metallurgy*, 2013, **2**, 47.
27. I. Langmuir, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 1918, **40**, 1361.
28. H. M. F. Freundlich, *Zeitschrift fur Physikalische Chemie-Leipzig*, 1906, **57**, 385.
29. A. A. Attia, S. A. Khedr and S. A. Elkholy, *Brazilian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, 2010, **27**, 183.
30. M. M. Dubinin, E. D. Zaverina and L. V. Radushkevich, *Zhurnal Fizicheskoi Khimii*, 1947, **21**, 1251.
31. A. U. Itodo and H. U. Itodo, *Life Science Journal-Acta Zhengzhou University Overseas Edition*, 2010, **7**, 31.
32. M. F. Sawalha, J. R. Peralta-Videa, J. Romero-González and J. L. Gardea-Torresdey, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 2006, **300**, 100.
33. P. Atkins, "Physical Chemistry", 6th ed., Oxford University Press, London, 1999, pp. 857-864.
34. M. Khraisheh, M. A. Al-Ghouti and C. A. Stanford, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 2010, **161**, 114.
35. X. Yuan, J. Liu, G. Zeng, J. Shi, J. Tong and G. Huang, *Renewable Energy*, 2008, **33**, 1678.
36. M. S. Tanyildizi, D. Āzer and M. Elibol, *Process Biochemistry*, 2005, **40**, 2291.
37. Q. K. Beg, V. Sahai and R. Gupta, *Process Biochemistry*, 2003, **39**, 203.